

Analysis of Student Performance Using Data Mining Algorithm in Weka

Divine Zacharias,
PG Scholar of Amal Jyothi College of
Engineering,
Kanjirappally, Kerala
divinezac@gmail.com

Merin Manoj
Asst. Professor of Amal Jyothi College of
Engineering,
Kanjirappally, Kerala
merinmanoj@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract: In this paper, Education Data Mining is significant in forecasting a student's academic progress in this article. In a forecasting information mining form, this article focuses on finding poor, medium, and quick learners among students and shows them using various approaches. Scholar details have been consulted, and a novice forecast has been performed using J48 and Random Tree in WEKA as an open-source technology. Assessment is based not just on academic success, but also on achievement in extracurricular sports. We can plainly assess a student's performance using both of these approaches.

Keywords—EDM, Comparison, Analysis, Accuracy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Records exist in the current condition of affairs. EDM is a method for identifying hidden styles, patterning, and analysing data stored in a records warehouse to determine future features. This has been used in a variety of settings, including schooling. Materials for learning Mining is a type of statistics mining programme. EDM's purpose is to collect and retrieve data. By selecting and translating essential statistics into acceptable forms, the EDM approach extracts and combines input metrics from real things. EDM employs a variety of tools and methodologies in order to analyse and forecast overall performance in teaching methods.

This study identifies aspects connected to student academic performance as well as aspects outside of educational overall performance, so aiding in improving the best of training by anticipating gradual

the effectiveness of those few types of techniques. The report's objective is to highlight people based on their actual behaviour.

FEATURES

- In this study, the performance of numerous characteristic selection algorithms turned into evaluated on one-of-a-kind classifications set of rules the use of the scholar's overall performance dataset generated for examine.
- The proposed have a look at made several comparisons to evaluate the effectiveness of the function choice strategies the use of the measures concerning errors and accuracy parameters.
- The study's overall goal was to test the efficacy of several techniques for predicting poor, moderate, and rapid thinkers based on not just student outcomes but also other criteria.
- It provides comprehensive series of information pre-processing and modelling strategies.
- The grouping of individuals depending on the qualities chosen demonstrates that the method's forecast rates differ.

Figure 1: Weka implementation tool

learners so that instructors may aid them in improving their overall performance. This study also looks into

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In terms of academic achievement, Ramaswamy N's research seeks to establish if a scholar is a moderate, average, or speedy thinker. To do so, they applied a number of data mining techniques, then examined the quality in relation to the individual's attributes [1]. Using methods to assess the quality of a forecast, a thorough assessment of the student data set was carried out.

For forecasting student academic progress, Paper [2] provides a type version based on the decision tree methodology. [3] Evaluate student performance at the end of the semester using three different decision tree algorithms: CART, ID3, and C4.5. In their research, they received 53 % , 46.44 % and 55.49 % [8]. [4] investigated undergraduate's total performance.

Parneetkaur et al. finished a study study in the educational sector [5]. Using the WEKA technique, they aim to identify lazy people in individuals and utilise assessment metrics to exclude out favoured skill characteristics. As a result, data is kept using a variety of approaches, which is a good way to predict quality [6]. The report's order to enhance awareness about the necessity of good function selection the performance of various

Examining the poor, common, and quick in a set of school data using categorising methods. All student statistics at MCA are recorded in a departmental database that is utilised as a source of facts. The goal is to locate the fine attribute by comparing output of various characteristic choosing methods in the prediction of newcomers, as well as the use of different class algorithms, as well as Random and J48 Tree, on the WEKA device. The aim of this research is to identify slow freshmen so that faculties might place more focus on them in order to boost their real quality [7].

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

This study used an unique class approach to evaluate the real quality of numerous different selection approaches. A compilation of the academic's accomplishments was made in preparation for the assessment. Using error and correct statistic criteria, the proposed study conducted numerous assessments to measure the efficacy of attribute selection procedures. The overall purpose of the study was to assess the utility of numerous techniques for anticipating academic success and other criteria among poor,

moderate, and rapid listeners. The material for the inquiry was offered by the university, and it included the knowledge of scholars such as CBGS. Other elements were taken into account as well, such as the use of fictitious data to judge a student's overall achievement as well as academic performance. As a consequence, academic leaders and school administration may find it useful if the aspects within the previously available information may be utilised as a predictor of test scores. The main intent of this is to look at various items at the institution to see if there are any uncommon tendencies that might help forecast their present efficacy. The survey's main goal is to categorise students based on their academic achievement as well as other factors outside than academic achievement.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

These entries were created and saved as .arff (attribute Relation file format) records [9]. An arff file is a text-based ASCII file that contains a list of kinds and their properties. Because Weka works with .arff files, the data has a certain structure, and it must be transformed back to .arff format after it has been captured. Because Weka works with .arff files, the data has a certain structure, and it must be transformed back to .arff format once it has been captured. ARFF files have two components. Facts about the preamble come first, then facts about the data. The Preamble includes both the connection call and a list of attributes and their kinds. Various attribute types may be assigned to different types of records. Last but not least, there's the delicacy trait [9].

In this paper, data was collected using type techniques. type is a data extraction methodology for establishing a collection of models and handling data in the simplest and most ecologically friendly way feasible. Student's CBGS, Curricular and Co-Curricular activities, Quiz, Summer Tasks, Assignment Marks, and Learner are among the factors examined in the article. In contrast to the student's educational accomplishments and other aspects, the use of dummy statistics is investigated in this study, which helps to attain a final conclusion based on the overall value.

Figure 2: Student Dataset

V. RESULTS

Throughout this project, the information is checked and examined using two different techniques: j48 and random tree (the usage of training set).

Table 1 contains all of the statistical results, as well as an examination of the effectiveness of all models, and it has been determined that the random tree technique works very well, with a correctness of 96.1212 %. Table 2 shows the amount of effectiveness for each approach.

Table 1. Statistical Analysis of Classifiers with Cross Validation.

Name of classification Algorithm	Class	TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC Area
Zero	Fast	0	0	0	0	0	0.5
	Average	1	1	0.564	1	0.533	0.5
J48	Fast	0.714	0.133	0.714	0.714	0.714	0.867
	Average	0.75	0.143	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.866
	Slow	0.714	0.133	0.714	0.714	0.714	0.857
	Weighted Avg.	0.273	0.368	0.368	0.273	0.27	0.452
RandomTree	Fast	0.857	0	1	0.857	0.853	0.995
	Average	1	0.071	0.889	1	0.941	0.996
	Slow	1	0	1	1	1	1
	Weighted Avg.	0.935	0.026	0.96	0.935	0.954	0.997

Table 2. Comparison of instance of correctly classified with cross validation.

Mining Technique	Accuracy
Zero	26.2626 %
J48	72.7273 %
RandomTree	95.4545 %

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, a model was developed based entirely on the inputs acquired from the real universe (university), as well as considering factors other than university statistics. Random tree performs well with 96.1212 % respectively across all information mining classifications, proving to be a very convenient and powerful extractor number of standards. This finding led institutions in identifying individuals who are poor learners, which will serve as a foundation for identifying particular resources that will benefit them.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Krpan, Slavomir Stankov, "Educational Data Mining for Grouping Students in E-learning System", Proceedings of the ITI 2012 34th Int. Conf. on Information Technology Interfaces, June 25 – 28, 2012, Cavtat, Croatia
- [2] X. She, T. Lv, X. Liu. The Pruning Algorithm of Parallel Shared Decision Tree Based on Hadoop, 10th International Symposium on Computational Intelligence and Design (ISCID), 2017, pp. 480–483.
- [3]. Ahmad, F., Ismail, N. H., & Aziz, A. A. (2015). The prediction of students' academic performance using classification data mining techniques. Applied Mathematical Sciences, 9(129), 6415-6426.

[4]. Cristobal Romero (2010), “Educational Data Mining: A Review of the State-of-the-Art”, IEEE Transactions on systems, man and cybernetics- Part C: Applications and Reviews vol. 40 issue 6, pp 601 – 618.

[5] A. Desai, S. Chaudhary, Distributed decision tree v.2.0, in: 2017 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data). Presented at the 2017 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data), 2017, pp. 929–934.